

Set up of a rapid identification method for nervous necrosis virus (NNV) variants circulating in Southern Europe

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Nervous Necrosis Virus (NNV) represents one of the most threatening pathogens for Mediterranean aquaculture due to its economic impact in the finfish industry. Currently, the RGNNV genotype and the RGNNV/SJNNV reassortant are the most widespread strains in Southern Europe with a more limited diffusion of the SJNNV genotype and the SJNNV/RGNNV reassortant. So far variants identification is based on genome amplification and sequencing, however this approach is quite time consuming. In recent years, multiplex PCR assays have gained popularity due to its convenience in terms of cost and time.

The aim of this study was to develop and validate a one-step multiplex RT-PCR (mRT-PCR) as a rapid diagnostic technique to detect NNV and to discriminate between RGNNV and SJNNV genotypes from their reassortant strains RGNNV/SJNNV and SJNNV/RGNNV.

In order to design optimal primer pairs NNV genome alignments were generated and primer candidates were selected according to their position within each genotype's RNA sequence, melting temperature (T_m) and generated amplicon size. New primers were combined together and with other seven primers already described in literature. The primers were tested and the mRT-PCR assay optimization was conducted with reference strains previously propagated on SSN-1 cell lines. Analytical sensitivity and specificity, and repeatability were also evaluated. Finally, the method was applied to European seabass (*Dicentrarchus labrax*) and gilthead sea bream (*Sparus aurata*) brain samples collected during disease outbreaks.

The mRT-PCR method efficiently identified the different NNV variants represented by the reference strains for RGNNV and SJNNV genotypes, and RGNNV/SJNNV and SJNNV/RGNNV reassortant strains producing one or two specific bands for each of them. The method showed a limit of detection ranging from $10^{2.3}$ to $10^{3.4}$ TCID₅₀ ml⁻¹ with the highest sensitivity for the RGNNV/SJNNV reassortant strain. Analytical specificity was tested towards several sea bass and bream pathogens (lymphocystivirus, *Vibrio anguillarum*, *Photobacterium damsela* subsp. *piscicida*, *Aeromonas veronii*) and showed no cross reactivity. The method resulted to be precise and robust providing overlapping results in intra- and interassay repeatability tests.

In conclusion, the developed mRT-PCR assay has revealed to be an accurate and rapid method for early identification of NNV variants circulating in Southern Europe.

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